

Formation Constants of Some Bivalent Metal Chelates of 2'-Hydroxy-4-Methoxy Chalcone

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The proton ligand formation constant of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy chalcone has been determined by spectrophotometric method. The mean value of $\text{PK}_a=11.40$ is found to be in 60% (V/V) aqueous dioxane and 0.1M ionic strength (NaClO_4). The stepwise formation constants for 1:1 and 1:2 complexes of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy chalcone with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) has been determined using various computational methods employing pH metric technique in 60% (V/V) aqueous dioxane and 0.1M ionic strength (NaClO_4). The order of stability is found to be $\text{Co(II)} > \text{Cu(II)} > \text{Ni(II)}$.

THE efficiency of chalcone as an analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric estimations of number of metal cations has been recognised^{1,2}. Very few complexes of chalcones are, however, been studied employing potentiometric methods. Recently Khadikar et al.³⁻⁷ have studied the chelate forming tendency of 2'-hydroxy and 2'-4'-dihydroxy-chalcones. In view of the usefulness of chalcones it would be of interest to study the chelating properties of other chalcones. The dissociation constant of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy chalcone and formation constants of its metal derivatives appear never to have been determined. In this communication such data are reported.

Experimental

2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy chalcone was prepared by the method described by Karrer et al⁸. (m.p. 92-93°) and were crystallised twice before use (Found C=75.44%, H=5.85%, Required C=75.59%, H=5.90%). All other chemicals used were of B.D.H. 'AnalaR' or equivalent quality. Since the chalcone is insoluble in water, dioxane-water mixture (60%V/V) was used as a solvent.

Standard solutions of the metal salts were prepared in double distilled water.

pH of the solutions were measured by using 'Plymetron Cl-41' pH meter with an accuracy of ± 0.05 pH units.

Spectrophotometric measurements were done by using 'Bausch and Lomb' Spectronic 20' spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The interaction M(II) with 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy chalcone (HL) causes a considerable lowering in pH and a pH-metric titration of 1:1 metal:ligand system has revealed an inflection at one equivalent of alkali indicating thereby the replacement of one proton as a result of chelation. The chelation reaction may be represented as

where M^{2+} stands for Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II).

pH metric titration of 1:2 and 1:3 mixtures of metal and ligand show inflection at two equivalents of alkali which corresponds to the formation of 1:2 complex in accordance with the reaction:

The inflection at two equivalents of alkali for 1:2 and 1:3 metal:ligand pH-metric titrations indicates the absence of polynuclear species. The absence of polynuclear species finds further confirmation in the determination of formation constants in different metal ion concentration. The formation constants thence obtained did not differ more than 0.05 log units.

For calculating the stepwise formation constants, using Irving-Rossotti¹⁰ method, the following solutions were prepared and total volume was made 50 ml.

- (3) HClO_4 (0.4434M, 2.5 ml) + NaClO_4 (1M, 3.20 ml) + ligand (0.05M, 10 ml) + metal salt solution (0.01M, 5 ml).

Calculated amount of dioxane and water is then added so that the medium is 60% (V/V) dioxane-water. The change in volume on mixing water and dioxane was determined by measuring the densities of the pure liquids and the mixtures as described by Irving and Rossotti¹⁵. The concentrations of the reactants were calculated with the allowance of this contraction and also for volume changes due to addition of alkali during the titration. Corrections for pH in aqueous-dioxane medium were made as described by Van Uiter and Haas¹¹. The titrations were also carried out with half the metal concentration prescribed above, but the formation constants thence obtained did not differ more than 0.05 and 0.07 log units from those determined at the higher metal concentration. This suggests an absence of any polynuclear species under the experimental conditions used in the present investigation.

The ligand used is a very weak acid. The shifting of the absorption peak from 350 nm in acid medium to 375 nm in alkaline medium could be utilised for determining its p^{Ka} value spectrophotometrically. Bower and Robinson method⁹ using dioxane-water mixture (60% V/V) as solvent at 22° and ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO_4) was used for the spectrophotometric determination of p^{Ka} . The mean value of p^{Ka} is found to be 11.40.

The stepwise formation constants of the complexes of the ligand with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) were determined employing Bjerrum-Calvin pH -titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰. A bulk electrolyte of 0.1 M sodium perchlorate was used to maintain constant ionic strength and reaction mixtures were all thermostated at $22 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

In calculating \bar{n} and $p^{(L)}$ the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values for \bar{n} and $p^{(L)}$ corresponding to different B-values (pH -metric reading) were calculated using the equations given in an earlier paper¹⁰.

The theoretical values of \bar{n} have been calculated¹⁵. In calculating the theoretical values of \bar{n} the corresponding values of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ obtained by half-integral method were used.

The experimental and theoretical formation curves were obtained by plotting the corresponding values \bar{n} against $p^{(L)}$. Both these formation curves did not differ within the experimental limit. The $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ were directly read from the formation curve using half-integral values of \bar{n} . In case of Co(II), \bar{n} , could not go beyond 1.099 and therefore the $\log k_2$ values were determined from the $p^{(L)}$ at $\bar{n}=1$ as discussed by Bjerrum¹⁴. The refined values of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ have also been determined by method of least square

and simultaneous equations. The results show that the values obtained by all these three methods are in good agreement.

The mean values of $\log k_1$, $\log k_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ along with $\log k_{av}$ and $\log k_1/k_2$ are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

	$\log K^*_1$	$\log K^*_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K^*_{av}$	$\log K_1/K_2$
Cu(II)	8.50	7.28	15.78	7.89	1.22
Ni(II)	5.63	4.56	10.20	5.10	1.07
Co(II)	8.77	7.50	16.27	8.13	1.23

* Mean values.

One would expect a bigger difference between $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ values in such ligands because of possible steric hindrance to the linking of the second ligand to the metal ion. The smaller difference may be due to trans structure (I):

As normally encountered, the average formation constants, $\log k_{av}$ (Table I) are consistently lower than $\log p^{k^H}$ (proton ligand formation constant) of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-chalcone. The perusal of Table I shows that the ratio $\log k_1/k_2$ is positive in all cases. Separation factors between first and second formation constants are well within the expected range and the absence of high values implies there is little or no steric hindrance to the addition of the second ligand molecule. This is in favour of the assignment of trans-structure(I).

Also, it is apparently indicated that there is almost equal tendency for the formation of neutral complex species ML_2 as for species ML^+ . Further, it is observed that the values of $\log k_2$ are lower than $\log k_1$ by 1.02-1.27 units. This suggests that in these systems not only the statistical effect (which gives the value of $\log k_1 - \log k_2 = 0.60$ units) should be considered but the electrostatic effect also becomes important¹⁵.

It will be interesting to compare the values of protonation constants and formation constants of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-chalcone with the corresponding values of 2'-hydroxy- and 2', 4'-dihydroxy-chalcones reported by us^{3,7}. The values of above mentioned constants are lower than those of 2'-hydroxy- and 2', 4'-dihydroxy-chalcones. This greater stability of 2'-hydroxy- and 2', 4'-dihydroxy chalcone complexes may

be attributed to the greater tendency of resonating structure for them as compared to 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-chalcone.

The perusal of Table 1 shows that the stability order is $\text{Co(II)} > \text{Cu(II)} > \text{Ni(II)}$. This order of stability follows neither the Irving-Williams' rule nor any of the empirical orders reviewed by Irving and William^{1,2}.

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